

Statistical Association between Temperature-Rainfall and Tea Yield at Sylhet Malnicherra Tea Estate: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract: Tea is one of the most important cash crops in Bangladesh, playing a significant role in the food security, poverty alleviation, employment and economy. As a rain-fed crop, tea cultivation depends on micro-climatic conditions for optimal growth. Bangladesh observed extreme weather and climate events over the last couple of decades. Bangladesh is experiencing the frequency of climate variations and extreme weather events, like prolonged drought, heavy rainfall, and late winter spells. The study area was carried out purposively at Malnicherra tea estate in Sylhet district to correlate the micro-climatic variables to tea productivity. The study also examines the trend of micro-climatic variables like maximum temperature, minimum temperature, and rainfall by using the time series data from 2012 to 2017. The simple linear regressions reveal that temperature and rainfall influence tea production. The tea production was negatively impacted by drought and excessive rainfall. Heavy rains eroded the top fertile soil and washed away soil nutrients. The yield of tea leaf is declining at the rate of 110.8 kg/ha/year. There was a high negative relationship between mean maximum temperature and yield of tea. The study recommends an integrated adaptive measure to minimize the adverse effects.

Keywords: Rainfall, Temperature, Relationship, Adaptation, Influence

Introduction

Tea is a perennial, evergreen, woody plant that grows worldwide of wide adaptability in a range of climates and soils. Tea ecosystem is an agro-ecosystem comprising tea plant, shade tree and other ancillary crops along with various abiotic elements. The life processes of biotic community are critically balanced with the tea biosphere, which includes climate and soil. The leaves are processed to prepare a non-alcoholic beverage popularly known as 'tea'. Tea is the cheapest beverage and occupies the second position in the world next to water in terms of consumed liquid (Dutta 2014, Marx et al. 2017). Tea is one of the most important cash crops in Bangladesh, playing a significant role in our economy, earning foreign currency, employment, poverty alleviation, and food security (Mamun 2011). It is a long established plantation crop of enormous importance to Bangladesh meeting the entire domestic demand of this cheapest health beverage. Bangladesh obtained 8th, 10th and 12th position in the world in terms of area, production and export of tea respectively (ITC 2015). Now, there are 162 tea estates in Bangladesh covering about 59,018 hectares of land and producing about

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85.05 million kg of finished tea per annum with an average yield of about 1,587 kg per hectare (BTB 2017).

As a rain-fed crop, tea cultivation depends on micro-climatic conditions for optimal growth. It is reported that the weather in the South Asia is becoming more stressful, more severe and less predictable: longer droughts; uneven heavier rainfall, more hail; and storms (IPCC 2013, IPCC 2014). Bangladesh observed extreme weather and climate events over the last couple of decades. Bangladesh is experiencing the frequency of climate variations and extreme weather events, such as prolonged drought, high daily precipitation, and late winter spells (Acharjee et al. 2019; Acharjee et al 2017; Chowdhury & Ward 2004; Murumkar et al. 2013; Mojid et al. 2015). Bangladesh for its geographical location is one of the most vulnerable countries for climate change (Mishra et al. 2019). Ochieng et al. (2016) found that tea will be one of the most adversely crops affected by climate change. Tea plant in their natural environment often experiences sequential and multiple stresses, that can affect the productivity (Eric et al. 2019). Both biotic and abiotic stresses reduce leaf production (Cheruiyot et al. 2010). It responds to abiotic stresses such as drought with dramatic changes in production (Niinemets 2015). The concentrations of metabolites produced by the tea plant are highly affected by the drought (Eric et al 2019; Kfoury et al. 2018; Han et al. 2017; Ahmed et al. 2014; Cai et al. 2013). Increasing temperatures and extreme weather events are posing a great threat to the existing production systems of tea. The pattern, distribution and frequency of monsoonal rainfall greatly affect the quality of tea as well as quantity of yield (Wijeratne et al. 2007). The rainfall distribution and the average annual maximum temperature in all producing seem to have undergone remarkable changes in the recent time (Dutta 2014). Therefore, there is a crying need to develop an integrated adaptive measure to cope with the changing climate. The study attempted to assess the impact of the change micro-climatic parameters on tea cultivation and to find out suitable technologies for adaptive measures.

Methodology

In Bangladesh Sylhet division is the major tea producing area, which is located in the delta of the Surma River. Sylhet district is situated between 23°59′ and 25°13′ North latitude and 90°54′ and 92°29′50″ East longitude. Malnichara tea estate was selected purposively as the study area, which is in the north-eastern part of this district. A tea garden at Malnicherra in Sylhet district was established in 1854 for commercial purpose (Redowan & Kanan 2013). Due to climatic condition and geographical position, North-eastern region of Sylhet district is the major tea leaves producing zones along with other agricultural crops. The time series data of 2012-2017 on the yield, rainfall, maximum temperature and minimum temperature were collected from this tea estate. Simple linear regression was done to correlate yield, rainfall and temperature.

Figure 1: Location of the study area (Malnicherra Tea Estate)

Results and Discussion

The trend of yield from 2012 to 2017

Figure 2: Trend of yield of tea at Malnicherra T.E. in Sylhet during 2012 to 2017

The mean yield per year from 2012-2017 of Malnichhara Tea Estate was 1320.2 kg/ha and it was declining at the rate of 110.8 kg/ha/year (Figure-1). The average yield was lower than average national yield (1,587 kg/ hectare) of Bangladesh (BTB 2017). Biggs et al. (2018) found the annual average yield of different gardens in Assam at <1500–2000 kg/ ha. Patra et al. (2013) found that productivity of green leaf in 2012 was reduced by 41.97 % and 30.90 %

as compared to 1993 and 2002, respectively in Indian Assam. The average annual yield of Malnichara tea estate from 2001-2011 was 1367.3 kg/ha (Ali et al. 2014). This indicates a clear declining trend of tea yield at Malnichara. Hick (2009) reported that Bangladesh was producing tea in declining trend from 2001 to 2006.

Figure 3: Average month-wise yield (2012-2017)

The highest production was observed in the monsoon (June-October) followed by the summer (March-June) and winter (October-March). The monsoon dynamics, temperature, solar radiation, and precipitation played as key drivers for the highest production in the monsoon (Boehm 2016). The month of August produced the highest amount of leaves followed July and June. In January production was lowest followed by February and March. The year begins and ends with dry periods in Bangladesh. Tea zones experience dry season from November to March while the rainy season continues from April to October and above 80% of annual rainfall is obtained during June – September (Paul et al. 2017). From the recent Meteorological report of Bangladesh, it is evident that in April-May the temperature reaches up to the maximum of 40⁰C whereas during the December or January the minimum temperature drops to the extent of 7.8⁰C. The impact of climate change is already witnessed in the declining trend of tea production. Most of the tea producing countries is characterized by distinct wet and or an alternate wet or dry season interspersed by temperature fluctuation from mild to severe. Bhagat et al. (2018) reported that tea producing countries in the world like China, India, Kenya and Sri Lanka have witnessed significant production due to climate events causing significant impact on economies and livelihood of dependents. It is projected that this change will continue with a greater pace in the upcoming days.

Effect of Rainfall on productions:

The figure-4 shows that the maximum rainfall (5779 mm) was recorded in 2017 though the yield was the lowest (1088 kg/ha). The low yield at very high rainfall is attributed to the lack of sun shine (Wijeratne et al. 2007). Excess water may negatively influence the production of tea due to saturation of soil, failure of absorption of water by plants. The rainfall was declining from 2012 to 2016. Despite highest rainfall in 2017, the production decreased as 2457.7 mm rainfall was recorded in the summer, while 895.4 mm in the winter. A drastic change in distribution of month-wise rainfall was observed (Figure-5). IPCC (2013) reported that the South Asian rainfall is subject to greater uncertainty.

Figure 4: The trend of yield and annual rainfall

The average rainfall in the month of monsoonal May reduced by 176.6 mm, where increased in the warmest April by 236.8 mm (Figure-5). Tea production is lower in long rains when compared with short rains. This is due to long rainy periods reducing the photosynthesis of the leaves with the decrease sunshine. Extreme rainfall negatively affect tea yield (Wijeratne et al. 2007, Esham and Garforth 2013; Duncan et al. 2016).

Figure 5: Changes in rainfall month-wise rainfall distribution pattern over 2012-2017

Therefore, the rainfall could not influence the production of tea. The tea leaf production and respectively rainfall was slightly correlated and had negatively influence on each other (Figure-6). The standard annual rainfall for the highest tea leaf production per hectare in Bangladesh is 4000–4600 (Ali et al. 2014). Tea generally exhibits a positive correlation between rainfall and its production depending on suitable temperatures and rainfall patterns (Ochieng et al. 2016). Any significant change in rainfall affects production.

Figure 6: Correlation between rainfall and yield (2012-2017)

Boehm et al. (2016) also reported that increased rainfall affects the tea yield. Figure-6 also showed decreasing tea yield returns to increased rainfall. Increased cloud cover associated with rainfall may hinder tea bush growth and difficulty arises in harvesting in that situation (Boehm et al. 2016).

Effect of temperature on yield

The Malnicherra Tea Estate experienced the highest yield and annual minimum temperature along with the lowest annual maximum temperature in 2012, while the contrary scenario in 2017 (Figure 4 & 7). Figure 7 shows that maximum annual temperature was increasing from 2012 to 2017, while annual minimum was decreasing. This is a signal of increasing temperature under a changing climate (Mathison et. al. 2013, Hijioka et al. 2014). The annual maximum and minimum temperature influence the tea yield widely (Duncan et al. 2016). The temperature above 26.6°C affects tea yield (Duncan et al. 2016) and below 12.5 °C negatively impacts the tea production (Tanton 1982). Wijeratne et al. (2007) reported that around 22°C temperature gave the highest yield of tea. Ali et al. 2014 found the range 23-25°C for the highest production.

Figure 7: The trend of annual maximum and minimum temperature (mean)

We observed that decreasing returns at the greater pace to warming and cooling impacting negative yield (Figure 8 & 9). The figure 7 shows highest negative correlation between tea yield and increased annual maximum temperature. On the other hand, there was a highly positive relationship between the yield and increased annual minimum temperature (Figure 9).

The temperature significantly impacts the tea yields (Boehm et al. 2016). Increased maximum temperature causes alterations in the leaf phenotype and significantly decreases the net photosynthetic rate and tea yield (Li et al. 2015). The temperature above the optimal range reduces the productivity of tea plantations (Dutta 2014, Gunathilaka et al. 2017 Wijeratne et al. 2007). Up to 40% yield loss of tea is expected by the end of the 21st century temperature increase (Adhikari et al. 2015).

Figure 8: Correlation between yield and maximum temperature

A hotter and wetter climate has a detrimental effect on tea yield (Gunathilaka et al. 2017). Recent researches on climate change revealed that the micro-climatic variables are becoming

extreme and intense, more erratic and less predictable accompanied by prolonged dry periods; heavier continuous rainfall over many days; more thunderstorms; and storms.

Figure 9: Correlation between yield and annual minimum temperature

The changes in rainfall pattern and the increasing trends of average maximum temperatures in all main tea producing regions were observed in the recent past (Dutta 2014). The tea productions are affected by both excess and shortage of water and suffer from heat stress (Marx et al. 2017). Changing climate is affecting the quality of tea as well as the dilution of phytochemicals is the consequence of heavy rainfall causing the change in the taste of tea. It also deteriorates the tea quality (Han et al. 2017). Climate change decreases not only the quality but also the quantity of tea yield through increasing soil erosion, pests' infestations, and outbreaks of diseases (Wijeratne 1996). The authors state that tea production depends on stable temperatures and consistent rainfall distribution patterns and anything excess would negatively affect the quality and quantity of tea production.

Adaptive measures

The declining trend of tea production may result in negative economic and social consequences, specially for tea producers, workers and traders. Tea producers need to take adaptive measures to cope with the existing and upcoming challenges. Most of the researchers of the world focused on taking adaptive measures to face the consequences of climate change. Some proposed adaptive measures are given below:

- a) **State policies and strategies:** Effective integrated and coordinated government policies or strategies focusing on climate adaptation are required to cope with the changing environment.
- b) **Collaboration and networking:** National networks involving multi and interdisciplinary research and communication units can be established for assessing the impacts of climate change.
- c) **Improved irrigation and drainage systems:** The drainage and irrigation systems should be improved to protect the plants from water logging and drought respectively.
- d) **Awareness building:** Public awareness about climate change, its impact on the tea sector and probable adaptive measures should be built.

- e) **Extension of adaptive measures:** Climate change adaptation measures should be wide spread immediately. Adopting indigenous and community-based measures and knowledge should be encouraged. New adaptation measures should be demonstrated before extension nationally.
- f) **Capacity building:** The scientists and managers should be trained on new technologies and management practices.
- g) **Crop insurance:** Small scale tea producers should be encouraged to purchase meteorological disaster insurance to transfer the risks to monetary compensations.
- h) **Introducing new varieties:** Drought and heat stress tolerant varieties should be introduced.
- i) **Integrated nutrient management:** A depletion of organic matter affects the water holding capacity of the soil. Integrated nutrient management is a practice where all sources of nutrients namely organic, inorganic and bio-fertilizer are combined and applied to the soils. It gives optimum crop nutrition, optimum functioning of the soil health and minimum nutrient losses or other adverse effect on the environment.
- j) **Mulching:** Mulching with succulent vegetative parts should be done at the time of new plantations, in young tea and in mature tea. Mulching immediate after the rainy season can conserve the soil moisture during the dry season. Mulching conserves soil moisture through reducing evaporation losses, surface run-off and soil erosion. Mulching minimizes the soil temperature in summers. Guatemala and Napier grass, aquatic plants, wild herbs and shrubs, and the barks of timbering plants are highly used for mulching.
- k) **Retaining pruning litter and shade tree droppings:** As a shade loving plant, tea plant needs optimum shade in the plantation area. During the summer in Bangladesh, most of the time temperature prevails above of the congenial temperature for tea production. Optimum shade reduced leaf temperature by 10-12°C at mid-day (Gee et al. 1982). Hence, proper shade tree establishment in the plantation area of Bangladesh can be an effective way to mitigate the affect of climate change. Retaining pruning litter is the easiest way of recycling crop residues. The pruning litter and shade tree droppings add considerable amount of organic matter to the soil.

Conclusions:

This research has used a tea garden level dataset of monthly yield, rainfall, maximum and minimum temperature. Other micro-climatic variables like humidity, average temperature, day length, sunshine and soil properties were not considered. But this dataset provides an ample opportunity to identify the causal effect of climatic variation on tea production. We show that tea productions are decreasing with the increase of maximum temperature and decrease of minimum temperature. This indicates that the tea gardens will be less productive under changing warmer climates. We show that the high annual cannot ensure high yield, rather excessive precipitation had a negative effect on the production. Bangladesh has witnessed a significant impact of climate change and it will continue in greater pace in the near future. Climate change does not mean only the rising temperature and erratic rainfall; it includes the extreme weather events like drought, fog, Nor'westers/tornado, thunderstorm and cyclones. Tea production in Bangladesh is directly linked to poverty alleviation (SDG 1), food security (SDG-2), good health (SDG 3), giving women equal rights to economic resources (SDG 5) and decent work (SDG 8). On the other hand, SDG 13 describes the actions for coping with climate change, where SDG-1 (target-1.5) emphasizes on building resilient society to absorb

the shock arising from climatic events. Considering all aspects effective and affordable adaptive measures have been recommended to reduce the sensitivity of tea productivity.

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